

MBSE in Ship Design: A critical systematic review - the case for Systems Element Analysis methodology

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Abstract. The technology push and new operations pull require ship design to account for uncertainties in all layers of the systems architecture (SA): Operations (O), Functions (F), Logical Architecture (L), and Physical Architecture (P). This uncertainty creates the need for a deeper understanding of the interrelations between the layers, especially in the context of early-stage ship design, where the requirements are set. Model-based systems engineering (MBSE) is proposed to explore the uncertainties within the SA. However, the level of adoption of MBSE in ship design for this purpose remains underexplored in the literature and inconsistently applied in industry. Specifically, the use of MBSE in creating and analyzing SA in ship design studies is in question. This systematic literature review aims to address this gap by identifying the key aspects of MBSE in the field and evaluating whether the current State-of-the-Art (SoA) aligns with the industry's needs. Based on the results of this literature review, this paper proposes a refinement to the Systems Element Analysis (SEA) method, a novel Finite Elements Method (FEM)-inspired MBSE method, aiming to confront the shortcomings of the current SoA. The proposed method explores the problem space encompassing all possible combinations of SA elements to study and analyze the interdependencies within SA quantitatively. SEA aims to unlock the FEM mathematical toolbox for systems architecture in ship design. The goal is to create a mathematical description of the problem space to explore it with the FEM toolbox.

Key words: ship design, model-based systems engineering (MBSE), systems architecture, literature review, systems elements analysis (SEA)

1. Introduction

Naval ships often represent the latest advancements in naval architecture. In light of recent geopolitical developments, the need for maritime ship designs incorporating new technologies has arisen. The evolving requirements of naval vessels have spurred the creation of designs prioritizing modularity and versatility [1]. However, this approach has led to designs that do not excel in any specific function [1]. The adaptation of innovative technologies and practices has also presented significant obstacles, for instance, in the Littoral Combat Ship (LCS) class of the US Navy, where the goal was to produce a small, adaptable frigate-sized warship that could reach crisis zones very quickly, with a required cruising speed of 40 knots, and be outfitted for the specific mission with mission modules [2, 3, 4].

The challenges encountered in the ship design process are frequently attributed to misalignments or ambiguities in the requirements, which are integrated during the Early-Stage Ship Design (ESSD) phase, as it significantly impacts the vessel's performance and feasibility. This phase affords engineers the most significant degree of design freedom at the lowest associated cost, as illustrated by [5]. However, in ESSD, most of the costs for the remainder of the project are settled, and faults made in this stage can carry on and even expand in later phases. This highlights the importance of understanding the interactions among the elements of the Systems Architecture (SA), which includes the ship, the operations and functions it performs, and the requirements established by stakeholders. This perspective contrasts with the traditional focus on the physical aspects of the vessel, commonly emphasized in naval architecture.

This need for a more holistic ship design methodology accounting for all aspects of the SA, as demonstrated by [6, 7], creates the initial question of "what is the Systems Architecture?". This question is at the

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center of this study as the definition of the SA remains a topic that creates “discourse” among naval architects and system engineers, which this paper aims to address. The different definitions of the SA given in both systems engineering and naval architecture papers will be explored in order to converge to a definition suitable for communication between the two fields and avoid creating a “universe of discourse”, as it is defined by [8], usually encountered in multidisciplinary project teams.

As per [7], the State-of-the-Art (SoA) of ship design lies in a multitude of methods, a few of them being Digital-Twin (DT), Simulation-Driven Design (SDD), Set-Based Design (SBD), Concurrent Design (CD), and Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE). These methods aim to address different shortcomings of the - although dated - more commonly used design spiral. Focusing on the ESSD, the methodology that stands out is MBSE, which is often seen as the SoA in other industries, like aerospace, as it allows for the exploration of the SA as a whole. Recently, there have been attempts to combine MBSE with Multi-Disciplinary Optimization (MDO) [9], which allows for the creation and exploration of the design space in terms of alternative systems. However, this constrained view of the design space disregards variability in the other layers of the SA, which is essential in ESSD, especially in the naval domain [1].

This paper presents the research gaps around MBSE, the method most commonly utilized to create the SA, in ESSD, specifically the Concept Exploration (CE) phase, and proposes a Finite Element Method (FEM)-inspired analogy approach for exploring the concept’s design space to address these gaps, named Systems Element Analysis (SEA) and introduced in [10]. The research gaps, identified via a literature review, reveal a focus on practical applications of MBSE. The central gap this paper aims to fill is the lack of a methodology that can quantitatively show the interrelations and interdependencies of the elements of the SA and create insights into the characteristics of the design space. This paper focuses on the interactions inside the elements of a vessel’s SA. The proposed SEA method holds the potential to be used beyond the understanding of the design space. It could potentially act as the basis for the better comprehension and quantification of the impact of uncertainty in the SA, including the semantically translated regulations and design rationals [11].

2. Literature Review

MBSE is recognized by [12] as an increasingly adopted methodology within the Systems Engineering (SE) community. The use of MBSE is increasing, especially for the validation phase of projects and concepts, where formal guidelines and policies are creating a demand for further and deeper understanding of the interrelations within the complex systems[13, 14]. This increase in demand is also reflected in the number of publications, presented in Figure 1.. Following the “development stages” as described by [15] for Digital Twins, it can be assumed that the incubation stage lasted until 2010, and the industry is now in the “growth” stage. Yet, recent literature reviews on MBSE [13, 16] recognize that the adoption by industry is centered around certain organizations [17]. In contrast, its more widespread adoption still requires significant effort [13]. This effort aims to overcome obstacles like the dominance of the defense and aerospace industries. The perception of MBSE as solely a tool instead of a method to understand complex systems [13, 18], instead of the combination of a tool, language, and method, as defined by [12]. This perception is further supported by the inconsistency, or even total lack of an underpinning mathematical foundation in the literature regarding MBSE, as demonstrated by [13].

In maritime engineering, especially in industry, there appears to be a peak in interest in the use of MBSE. MBSE is presented in the ship as a solution to visualize the multitude of interconnections between the components present in a vessel, and a method to address the uncertainty stemming from these connections. However, as seen in Figure 1., it is safe to suggest that MBSE is still in its “incubation” stage. Specifically for ship design, MBSE has been used in naval acquisitions. Specifically, US Navy [19] and Dutch Ministry of Defence [18]. Supporting the claim that MBSE is still in its infancy in ship design, with the exception of a literature review on the concept design of US Naval Ships [20], two MSc thesis on the topic [21, 22], and a PhD Thesis literature review [23], no recent literature reviews have been published to assess the SoA and the level of adoption of MBSE in the ship design community. To address this and to identify the research gaps in this field, a systematic literature review is conducted below in Section 2.1..

Figure 1.: MBSE Research Categories per Year in Dimensions.ai

2.1. Systematic Literature Review

This systematic literature review follows the approach detailed by [24]. The research question this process aims to answer is: “What is the SoA in the creation and analysis of SA using MBSE in ESSD?”. However, as can be observed in Table 1., the publications for the SA and the additional aspect of SA under uncertainty, which is present in ESSD, in ship design are a very narrow field, thus this systematic literature review focuses on the wider field of MBSE in ship design as presented in Table 1.. To properly address the literature review question, the following literature sub-questions (LQ) have been introduced:

LQ-1. What is the status of MBSE in Ship Design?

LQ-2. What vessel’s lifecycle phase MBSE is focused on?

LQ-3. What is the definition of the term *Systems Architecture* in Systems Engineering and Ship Design?

LQ-4. How is MBSE used in Ship Design under uncertainty?

LQ-5. How is MBSE used in the Concept Exploration phase?

2.1.1. Methodology

A preliminary search was performed on the Dimensions.ai database with the queries in Table 1., focusing on including these keywords in the title and abstract of the contributions. This strategy is used to extract an initial mapping of the literature regarding the evolution of the field and the concepts explored. Moreover, ship design and MBSE were examined stoichiometrically separately and explored bibliometrically. The result of this exploration is discussed in Section 2.1.2.. Following this, an additional systematic literature search was performed on the Scopus and Web of Science databases for the first query of “MBSE & Ship Design”, as presented in Table 1.. This resulted in a starting set of 55 publications from Dimension.ai, 37 on Scopus, and 44 on WoS. It is worth noting that no naval architecture-specific databases were utilized. However, the majority of these subject-oriented databases are included in the Dimensions.ai. The resulting sets were subsequently merged, resulting in a set of 79 papers. The inclusion criteria from [25] were introduced to refine this resulting literature set. Given the limited number of results of the queries, no Quality Criteria, as described by [26], were used. Instead, the following inclusion criteria were added to the ones from [25]:

- C-1. Argument is pertinent to the marine section (inclusion)
- C-2. Full text in English is available (inclusion)
- C-3. The article is a primary study (inclusion)
- C-4. The study is a duplicate (exclusion)
- C-5. Irrelevant to MBSE(*exclusion*).
- C-6. The search terms are used, but the actual semantics are inconsistent (*exclusion*).

Table 1.: Search Queries and Number of Results

Search Query	Number of Results
(MBSE OR "Model?Based System? Engineering" OR "Model-based paradigm?") AND (ship OR naval OR vessel) AND (design OR concept*)	55
(MBSE OR "Model?Based System? Engineering" OR "Model-based paradigm?") AND (ship OR naval OR vessel) AND (design OR concept*) AND ("system* architecture" OR "system* design" OR "integration framework?" OR "network of system*")	10
(MBSE OR "Model?Based System? Engineering" OR "Model-based paradigm?") AND (ship OR naval OR vessel) AND (design OR concept*) AND uncertainty	2

This process, shown in Figure 2., ensures that only relevant literature is included in the final study. The resulting set of publications includes 24 papers, presented in Table 2.. The majority of the excluded papers were due to the lack of access and actual connection to the marine sector. Regarding the lack of access, most of the excluded publications were either book chapters or published by publishers to whom TU Delft did not provide access as of this paper's writing. The next step in answering the literature research questions is to classify the works' content to separate the different knowledge areas. This study proposes a two-dimensional categorization of the works' content, a "methodology" axis, and a "scope" axis. The methodology axis is discretized based on the method used and the depth of the methods used, and includes the following categories:

- *MBSE use-case*: a simple concept or case study of MBSE methodology for the design of a System or a System-of-Systems
- *MBSE methodology advancement*: prioritizes the advancement of the methodology involved in MBSE in terms of software, tools or methods
- *MBSE & Optimization*: including an optimization problem in the case study
- *Design Space Exploration*: focuses on exploring the design space, not optimizing a solution. Includes sensitivity and/or elasticity studies.

The "scope" axis spans the different focus levels of the case study, with the following categories:

- *Fleet Level*: explores the fleet as a compilation of systems-of-systems and the impact of a unit on the whole fleet.
- *Systems Architecture of Vessel*: focuses on a specific vessel but explores all the layers of the SA (OFLP)
- *Physical Layer of Vessel*: focuses mostly on the physical layer of the vessel, exploring the interaction of the systems
- *System of Vessel*: focuses on a single system onboard the vessel, disregarding the possible interactions with other systems

Figure 2.: Systematic Literature Review Approach

2.1.2. Stoichiometric Review of Ship Design and MBSE

Ship Design

The field of ship design is showing a growing interest, as illustrated by the growth of publications in Figure 3.. This can be attributed to regulatory factors [25] that require vessels to become more environmentally friendly, approaching 2035 as set by the [27]. The year 2023 shows lower publication numbers than the previous years. The most intriguing observation can be drawn from the Figure 4., where we can see a general trend from the concepts of ship design, naval architecture, and design process to more specific concepts, like fluid dynamics, energy efficiency, ship resistance, and digital twin. The following conclusions can be drawn by examining the concepts in the Figure 4.a. To begin with, the connection between disciplines, illustrated by the different colored clusters, is minimal, with the only clusters that are distributed within the others are the *Design parameters* cluster, illustrated as blue, and, although less distributed, the *Optimization* cluster, depicted as yellow. This shows that naval architecture retains its status as highly traditional, with multidisciplinary publications being less numerous. This can also be attributed to the fact that ship design, with its traditional role, is mainly concentrated on the earlier phases of the design cycle, where the naval architect prefers to use low-fidelity, statistically derived approaches rather than high-fidelity ones. Moreover, we can see the ship design cluster in green color dominated by navy concepts, which reinforces the position that the SoA in complex ship design is found in the military domain.

Figure 3.: Publications per Year

MBSE

MBSE is a SE methodology and is a recently introduced term that is starting to pick up momentum, especially in the year 2022, see Figure 5.b. MBSE primarily belongs to the field of Systems Engineering, which

Figure 4.: Ship Design Concepts

can also be observed in the central cluster of Figure 5.a. The only exception to that cluster is the yellow cluster, which can be named *the Automotive Cluster*. The automotive cluster suggests that the SoA in the simulation could be on the automotive industry. This contradicts the common belief that the SoA in MBSE is primarily rooted in the aerospace industry, as detailed in the IMDC 2024 Proceedings by [7]. The system design cluster (in red) shows the close connection between MBSE and system design, especially in the aerospace industry. Accounting also for the average date of the publications in Figure 5.b, the conclusion could be drawn that the industry, in general, is moving from the system’s design to the system’s simulation. Another observation made from this figure is the absence of terms such as operations, functions, and requirements, which can lead to the conclusion that MBSE is used for the detailed design of the system and not so much for the early concept design, as was concluded by [18].

Figure 5.: MBSE Concepts

2.2. Analysis of the Systematic Literature Review Results

Beyond the initial overview, the papers were further categorized based on their topic, the vessel’s lifecycle phase, and the technology readiness level (TRL). The topics were not introduced a priori but are based on the content of the final set of papers. Regarding the vessel’s lifecycle phase, since the focus of this paper is the concept exploration phase, a distinction needs to be made in the “design” phase. This classification is not meant to examine the level of detail in the studies; rather, it is concerned with the intended phase of the paper. The following phases are considered relevant:

- *Requirements Elucidation*: The requirements are explored and iterated in this phase. In naval acquisitions, this stage can coincide with the Contract Design [1].

- *Concept Exploration*: This phase aims at understanding trade-offs and mapping the design space of potential designs.
- *Concept Definition*: Concept Definition is about derisking the designs. The concept's design space has significantly shrunk compared to the Concept Exploration.
- *Detailed Design*: The advanced design phase, where the design is finalized. This phase usually coincides with the production phase in the ship design field.
- *Production*: Concurrent with Detailed Design. The difference with the detailed design phase is the focus on creating the actual ship, instead of the virtual representation of the vessel from the detailed design.
- *Operation*: Includes all the possible aspects of the operations of a vessel. It involves both the commercial shipping and naval aspects of operations and the vessels' maintenance and repair.
- *Decommission*: this phase marks the end of life for a vessel with her decommissioning and scrapping, or a big change in her function and usually her physical aspects with substantial retrofits.
- *Lifecycle*: for this category to be used, more than one of the phases above has to be examined. The phases from the Requirements Elucidation to the Concept Definition are considered as a single phase to identify a Lifecycle analysis.

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) describes the readiness of the publications' results or produced software to be used in industry, and in this paper, the following are distinguished according to [28]:

- *Concept*: Level 2 or below, where papers propose a potential concept and its application without proof-of-concept.
- *Paradigm*: Level 3, where an element concept is proposed and analytical models or computer simulations support its functionality.
- *Framework*: Level 4 and 5, where critical functions of the concept are identified and experiments are carried out to verify the effectiveness of the proposed concept. Scaling effects and relevant assumptions are identified and taken into account in the experiment, allowing for the inclusion of simulation experiments in the validation process.
- *Application*: Level 6 and above, where, minimally, the critical functions are verified and the concept's performance is demonstrated in the relevant environment, and the models are in a representative form, fit, and function.

When examining the final set of publications, the topics of interest were extracted and are presented as follows in alphabetical order:

- *Autonomous Navigation*: concerns with the aspects around autonomous navigation, mainly simulating the autonomous operations.
- *Combat Management System (CMS)*: discusses combat systems from UAV drones to conventional weapons onboard a naval vessel.
- *Decision Making*: relates to the decision-making regarding requirements, which systems to have onboard, and supporting operational decision making.
- *Deep-Sea Mining*: relates to technologies around deep-sea mining, from the design of the underwater drones, to the design of support vessels and the technologies involved in these.
- *Energy Systems*: includes the propulsion and electrical distribution systems, and concerns around their operation, design, decarbonization, and alternative propulsion systems.

- *Intelligent Monitoring*: concerns with IoT aspects, like telemetry, distribution system routing, and transport system management.
- *Layout*: explores the spatial aspects of ships, as well as what systems or components are included onboard.
- *Naval*: discusses aspects around the additional complexities stemming from the military scope of naval vessels. Involves the design of naval vessels and equipment, and the operations and interactions with other assets.

Table 2. presents the final categorization. The topics encountered range from the layout of deep-sea mining vessels to the autonomous navigation of unmanned surface vessels. Most publications aimed to assist in decision-making, mostly related to verifying and validating the requirements, as shown in Figure 6.a. Specifically, a small preference exists for exploring the systems architecture in decision-making, as indicated in Figure 6.b. As can be observed in Figure 6.c, they also focus on the concept definition and operations phase, not the requirements elucidation phase. Regarding the concept exploration phase, which is the emphasis of this paper, only one publication is presented. Additionally, as presented in Figure 6.d, the maturity of the proposed concepts is generally low, with most publications achieving at least the paradigm maturity level, or level 3 TRL, with the maximum being a TRL of 6. Finally, as observed in Figure 6.e, almost all papers aim to use MBSE as a tool to perform a case study, with only one paper interested in advancing the MBSE methodology and only two papers combining MBSE with optimization.

Table 2.: Categorization of the resulting set of publications

Paper Reference	Year	Publication Type	Methodology	Scope	Topic	Phase	TRL
Zirui et al.,[29]	2025	Article	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Decision Making	Detail Design	Concept
Qin et al.,[30]	2024	Proceeding	Case Study	System	CMS	Requirements Elucidation	Paradigm
Sullivan et al.,[31]	2024	Chapter	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Layout	Concept Definition	Concept
Nakashima et al.,[32]	2024	Article	Case Study	Physical Layer	Autonomous Navigation	Operation	Paradigm
De Haan et al.,[33]	2024	Proceeding	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Layout	Operation	Paradigm
Solheim et al.,[34]	2023	Article	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Deep Sea Mining	Concept Definition	Framework
Araujo et al.,[35]	2023	Proceeding	Case Study	Physical Layer	Energy Systems	Concept Definition	Framework
Cuzner et al.,[19]	2023	Proceeding	Case Study	Physical Layer	Energy Systems	Concept Definition	Paradigm
Souflis - Rigas et al.,[36]	2023	Article	Optimization	Physical Layer	Energy Systems, Layout	Concept Definition	Paradigm
Wilkins et al.,[37]	2023	Article	Optimization	Physical Layer	Energy Systems, Layout	Detail Design	Framework
Basnet et al.,[38]	2022	Article	Case Study	Physical Layer	Decision Making	Operation	Framework
Chu et al.,[39]	2022	Proceeding	Advancement	Physical Layer	Layout	Detail Design	Framework
Feng et al.,[40]	2022	Proceeding	Case Study	Physical Layer	CMS	Operation	Framework
Diatte et al.,[41]	2022	Article	Case Study	Physical Layer	Decision Making, Energy Systems	Concept Definition	Paradigm
Hifi et al.,[42]	2022	Proceeding	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Decision Making, Layout	Detail Design	Paradigm
Van Hien et al.,[43]	2021	Article	Case Study	Physical Layer	Naval	Detail Design	Framework
Georgopoulou et al.,[44]	2021	Chapter	Case Study	Physical Layer	Energy Systems	Operation	Framework
Lagemann et al.,[45]	2021	Proceeding	Case Study	Physical Layer	Energy Systems	Concept Exploration	Paradigm
Power et al.,[46]	2021	Proceeding	Case Study	Fleet	CMS, Naval	Operation	Paradigm
Beery et al.,[47]	2019	Article	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Mission Simulation, Naval	Operation	Framework
Tudor et al.,[48]	2019	Proceeding	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Naval, Layout	Concept Definition	Concept
Morris et al.,[49]	2018	Article	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Decision Making, Naval	Concept Definition	Paradigm
Arnould,[50]	2018	Proceeding	Case Study	Systems Architecture	Decision Making, Naval	Requirements Elucidation	Framework
Slaczka et al.,[51]	2017	Chapter	Case Study	Fleet	Intelligent Monitoring	Operation	Framework
Solazzi et al.,[52]	2012	Proceeding	Advancement	System	Decision Making, CMS	Operation	Concept

2.3. Detailed Analysis of the SoA of MBSE in Ship Design

After reviewing the papers presented in Table 2. and analyzing the results of the categorization in Section 2.2., it is feasible to answer the literature questions set in Section 2.1. and establish the state of MBSE in ship design. It has to be noted that the findings of the answers to the literature questions may initiate further, smaller-scale literature reviews that can deviate from the strict MBSE domain, to fully provide a complete explanation.

2.3.1. Answering LQ-1 - What is the status of MBSE in Ship Design?

MBSE has become an increasingly referenced methodology within maritime design literature. It is recognized as an essential methodology for tackling complex, multidisciplinary challenges in ship design [7, 18]. However, its practical implementation remains fragmented and primarily concentrated on specific physical subsystems or isolated operational aspects. Recent categorization of existing literature demonstrates that MBSE applications predominantly cluster around traditional topics such as energy efficiency,

Figure 6.: Results per Year Bar-Charts

propulsion systems, and fluid dynamics, with limited interdisciplinary integration or systematic exploration across broader ship design architectures, as discussed in Section 2.1.2..

Bibliometric analyses further highlight that the majority of MBSE-related publications are at conceptual or preliminary maturity levels. These studies frequently employ qualitative or simplified binary approaches

to describe interactions between system components rather than comprehensive quantitative methods. This methodological limitation restricts a thorough analysis of interdependencies across Operational, Functional, Logical, and Physical (OFLP) system layers.

Additionally, reviewed literature and categorization results indicate a predominant focus on discrete components or subsystems without substantial consideration of holistic system architecture or discrete operational aspects aimed at military purposes. Uncertainty management, required in the ESSD, is typically limited or absent, with static approaches to requirements and operational scenarios common in the reviewed cases [34, 36, 37]. Some advancements are noted in the use of SysML to enhance communication, traceability, and structured requirements definition; however, these remain relatively isolated and not fully integrated into comprehensive MBSE frameworks [32, 33].

Finally, while quantitative approaches, such as the heatmap correlation matrices proposed by [53], attempt to map component interactions, they still lack comprehensive methods for systematically exploring alternative designs and addressing uncertainty beyond binary correlations.

2.3.2. Answering LQ-2 - What vessel's lifecycle phase MBSE is focused on?

MBSE in literature has been strongly linked with the concept design, especially in the earlier phases, like requirements elucidation and concept exploration [54]. A deviation from this is observed in the examined literature set, with most publications focusing on the concept definition and operation phases. It is worth highlighting that no publications on the production, decommissioning, and lifecycle phases were identified, and only one [45] was directed at the concept exploration phase. It is also worth mentioning that the detailed design phase first appeared in 2021, after which it consistently appears in the examined literature. This also aligns with a significant gain in MBSE publications in general in the literature, as can be observed in Figure 1.

Regarding the possible correlation between the lifecycle phase and the other categories used in this literature review, the most noteworthy observation is that for the earlier phases of ESSD there is a notable focus on the systems architecture scope. Even within the concept definition phase, for the publications on the verge of concept exploration, there is a trend of focusing on a greater, less focused scope. Additionally, for the publications on the operation phase, there is a distinction in the scope between the physical layer and the systems architecture layer, with the publications on the physical layer focusing on the function of a specific aspect of the vessel. The ones on the systems architecture layer focus on the interaction of the systems architecture with the mission at hand. It has to be emphasized that most publications on the operations phase either explore a naval topic or are indirectly connected with the naval industry. It is also noted that all publications directly linked to a naval topic have as their scope the systems architecture and aim to explore the effectiveness of the concept in a mission.

Summarizing the above observations, the earlier in ESSD or the later in the operation phase a publication is, the broader the scope is. This corresponds with the Validation and Verification model (V&V) found in the literature of systems engineering and software design [55, 56, 57]. Specifically, at the beginning of the concept development, the concept is explored as a whole to set requirements and analyze trade-offs. Following this, the focus shifts to a higher fidelity or depth of studies with a more limited scope. Finally, the scope expands again to validate the concept's functionality and effectiveness in the mission, either as a functional unit or as part of a fleet.

2.3.3. Answering LQ-3 - What is the definition of the term Systems Architecture in Systems Engineering and Ship Design?

Systems Architecture is a prevalent term in systems engineering and ship design, as observed in Figure 6.b, but its definition is inconsistent in the literature reviewed. Specifically, there is an evident inconsistency in the actual meaning of this term, and it is rarely defined before its use. This triggered a separate literature review including areas outside of MBSE and Ship Design, the results of which and the abovementioned inconsistency can be observed in the Table 3.. The list of references and their corresponding definitions originates from the systematic literature review. Systems architecture, generally, refers to the conceptual model that defines a system's structure, behavior, and functions. It involves designing and

arranging various subsystems and components within a ship to achieve desired functionalities and performance, considering operational and technical requirements [58, 59, 60].

The varied definitions of SA in Table 3. reveal significant inconsistencies across disciplines. These discrepancies have practical implications for communication, collaboration, and the effectiveness of system development processes. Key observations include:

1. **Diverse Focus Areas:** Definitions emphasize different aspects—structural arrangements [61, 62], functional allocation [21, 63], and behavioral or evolutionary properties [64, 65].
2. **Varying Levels of Abstraction:** Some offer abstract descriptions [21], while others detail physical, logical, and operational dimensions [59].
3. **Inconsistent Terminology:** Terms like “elements,” “components,” and “blocks” lack standardized meanings, causing confusion.
4. **Need for Formalization:** Some sources acknowledge the necessity for formal definitions but do not provide them [66], relying instead on external standards [67].

To better communicate this research to both naval architects and system engineers, the following definition will be used, bridging the definitions from the literature review in Table 3..

***Systems Architecture** is the abstract representation of a system, encompassing its components, relationships, and organizational principles. It serves as a framework to understand, analyze, and communicate the system’s structure, behavior, and evolution across operational, functional, logical, and physical dimensions.*

Table 3.: Systems Architectures Definitions

Definition	Reference	Science Field
The architecture of a system essentially is about the parts of the system and the connections between the parts.(...)The parts of each architecture seem to interact with one another in order to (help) achieve certain goals, which may be only implicit or explicitly stated as such.	Chung et al.,[61]	Software Engineering
System architecture is an abstract description of the entities of a system and the relationships between those entities.	A. Tepper,[21]	Naval Architecture
(..) architectures as ‘the scheme by which the function (..) is allocated to components’. Thus, depending on the level of abstraction with which they are considered, systems architectures may be viewed in terms of: (1) stakeholders’ expectations and lifecycle process requirements (requirements view), (2) functions that are arranged within the functional architecture (functional view) and (3) the sub-systems and components included within the design architecture (component view)	Bonjour et al.,[63]	Systems Engineering
We define the architecture of a system as the set of structures needed to reason about the system, which comprise elements, relations among them, and properties of both(..)	Klein et al.,[64]	Systems Engineering
The Systems Modeling Language (OMG SysML) has emerged as an open, international, and industry standard for representing the system architecture. (..) Elements in the SysML model can then be connected via model-based connections, as shown by blue radial arrows, to elements in other engineering tools, such as CAD, CAE, and requirements management. These connections provide services for model transformation, comparison, and synchronization as all the models evolve in a concurrent development environment.	Bajaj et al.,[68]	MBSE in Aerospace
System architecture determines the “arrangement of the functional elements into physical blocks	Eckert et al.,[62]	Systems Engineering
Three primary facets of a system are considered, the physical, logical and operational architectures. The architecture of a system is defined as the manner in which its components are organized and integrated. The physical architecture represents the spatial and physical characteristics of the system and of its environment. The logical architecture describes functional characteristics of the system, and the linkages between each component of the system. The operational architecture describes temporal behavior of a system, including human-system interactions to some extent.	Brefort et al.,[59]	MBSE & Naval Architecture
A system architecture formally represents a system designated to facilitate understanding by organizing relationships, processes, fundamental system components, constraints, and behaviors.	Madni et al.,[69]	MBSE
<i>This paper provides an overview of several formal definitions by IEEE and ISO standards, and conclude that:</i> architecture refers to “fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution.”	Dickerson et al.,[70]	Systems Engineering
The purpose of the architecture is to “assist the understanding of the system’s essence and key properties pertaining to its behaviour, composition and evolution”.	Odukoya et al.,[71]	MBSE & Naval Architecture
<i>This paper reviews SoS Architecture and defines SA as a set of decisions encoded as variables with a set of allowed alternatives. Many others equate architecture with a set of description models that are supported by architecture frameworks.</i>	Fang et al.,[72]	Systems Engineering
<i>Considers the systems architecture to be a formalization of MBSE, but without properly defining it.</i>	Lu et al.,[66]	MBSE
<i>Adopts the INCOSE definition found in Walden,[65]</i>	Stirgwort et al.,[67]	MBSE & Naval Architecture
The system architecture is a more abstract representation of the system, whereas the system design is focused on the implementation of compatible technologies that align with the requirements, structure, and behaviour described by the system architecture.	Walden,[65]	Systems Engineering

2.3.4. Answering LQ-4 - How is MBSE used in Ship Design under uncertainty?

Uncertainty in system requirements poses significant challenges in traditional systems engineering, particularly in complex projects such as naval vessel design, where requirements can evolve or be unclear from the start. MBSE can be used to address these challenges through its systematic use of models that encapsulate both the known aspects of systems and the flexibility to adapt to new information or changing requirements [73, 74]. Yet, uncertainty, as a mathematical concept, is encountered in the systematic literature review publications set only once [36]. In general, uncertainty, or unknown factors in the examined publications, is examined deterministically, by determining whether a change is propagated throughout the MBSE components included in the study. This lack of underpinning mathematics is in line with the conclusions from [13].

While MBSE enables the dynamic creation and modification of system models, allowing engineers to simulate and analyze different scenarios as new requirements emerge or existing ones change, it does not fully eliminate the challenges associated with uncertain requirements. Managing these uncertainties remains complex, and the systematic traceability from requirements through to design, implementation, and verification can still encounter obstacles in ensuring that all evolving requirements are adequately met [75, 76]. The visual and iterative nature of MBSE models aims to enhance communication among stakeholders; however, achieving a common understanding and alignment on project goals and technical approaches requires significant effort when dealing with uncertain requirements. Moreover, while MBSE supports the iterative refinement of models and allows for continuous integration and testing of new requirements, this iterative process cannot eliminate all risks associated with uncertainties or guarantee accurate forecasts of system behavior and performance.

Uncertainty in the architectural layers of complex systems continues to pose significant challenges, particularly when integrating multiple subsystems with intricate interdependencies. Although MBSE provides a structured and coherent framework intended to enhance communication and alignment among engineering teams across different domains [71], it does not resolve these uncertainties, opting for a deterministic approach. Technical, operational, and environmental factors can still introduce unpredictable influences on system behavior and performance over time [77]. As systems become increasingly complex, managing variants across different architectural levels remains critical and challenging. This complexity is further exacerbated by the need to accommodate evolving requirements, which can significantly impact the system architecture's functional and logical layers [74]. While advanced techniques such as stochastic modeling and scenario analysis can help mitigate these uncertainties, ensuring that the architectural layers remain robust and adaptable to future changes is still a challenging task [7, 78].

2.3.5. Answering LQ-5 - How is MBSE used in the Concept Exploration phase?

In recent years, MBSE has become an increasingly popular approach in exploring design spaces, particularly in complex systems architecture. However, as discussed in Section 2.3.2., only one paper was identified by the systematic literature review [45]. The maturity of this publication is limited, as a *paradigm*, and it is purely an MBSE case-study, with little discussion on the exploration of the SA design space, as seen in Table 2., and as such it cannot be used to establish the SoA and answer this literature question. Thus, literature beyond ship design was explored, specifically literature from the aerospace and defense industries.

As noted by [9], MBSE enables engineers to systematically explore design alternatives by integrating requirements, architecture, and behavior models into a coherent system representation. One of the key advantages of MBSE is its ability to handle uncertainties inherent in early concept exploration phases, such as this NASA process called Architectural Design Space Exploration (ADSE) by [9].

“MBSE in Architecture Design Space Exploration” used as an optimization algorithm for designing complex aeronautical systems to reduce development time and costs and increase the design's transparency, efficiency, and traceability. The method creates alternative system architectures by mapping functions to components to satisfy the requirements used as input. This is achieved using the morphological matrix method, which aims to show the interchangeability of the components needed to achieve the required functions. This is based on the method by [79], who present a process for architecture synthesis based on a function tree, which involves constructing a function tree from an iterative procedure that trades finding

solutions that fulfill a given function and inducing functions needed for implementing the chosen solution. This was improved with an Architecture Design Space Graph, which shows the chain of functions and components and characterizes the components and their instances with inputs and outputs, allowing for the automation of the morphological matrix. A similar mapping method, a knowledge graph based on the inputs and outputs of the components, was also utilized by [80].

A literature review of other design exploration publications was conducted to understand the field better. To start with, [81] explored using digital twins to generate and evaluate system architectures. This study focused on the collaborative aspects of the design process. [53] proposes a multi-objective design optimization method that creates a design space and uses a correlation matrix to explore the interdependencies between components. Similarly, [82] explores the quantitative evaluation of the possible architectures but focuses solely on the component level, using the requirements as input for the optimization. In the same wavelength, [83] combines MBSE with Set-Based Design to explore the trade-offs between design parameters. [84] focuses on early-stage design space exploration and trade-off analysis but lacks exploration of alternative components.

2.4. Conclusion of Literature Review

The literature clearly illustrates several critical gaps in current MBSE methodologies applied to ship design. The primary interpretation of these gaps is that existing MBSE applications do not adequately support comprehensive quantitative modeling of system interdependencies and uncertainties, particularly in evolving maritime operational contexts. This limitation significantly impacts the capability to systematically evaluate and optimize ship design architectures under realistic operational conditions. The specific gaps identified in this literature review are as follows:

- RG-1. Lack of methods describing the propagation of changes through all layers of system architecture beyond identifying affected components.
- RG-2. Absence of guidelines for effectively modeling uncertainty within the operational, functional, and logical layers of ship design.
- RG-3. Insufficient methods to systematically generate and explore design alternatives under uncertainty beyond the limitations of Pareto fronts.

These gaps, along with the observations regarding the state of MBSE, underline the need to rethink the ship design's priorities, goals, and general attitude towards MBSE. Specifically, provided that MBSE is only minimally used in ship design, there is the necessity to treat this new methodology as a guideline, not as an end-goal in-itself. MBSE should be a tool in the naval architect's quiver, with the goal being the synthesis of existing models, extraction of information, trends and sensitivities, to aid in the ship design process, especially in the ESSD.

Consequently, there is a compelling need for a more integrated, rigorous, and quantitative MBSE framework. These findings lead to the rationale for adopting the FEM analogy-based MBSE methodology, which was initially introduced in [10], and expanded on in Section 3., which aims to offer a structured, mathematically sound approach to exploring the systems architecture design space comprehensively, quantifiable, and systematically.

2.5. Reflection on the Systematic Literature Review

The systematic literature review conducted in the Section 2. identified three critical shortcomings in existing MBSE methodologies as applied to ship design. These gaps are naturally dependent on the result of the systematic literature review. This study proposed a methodology to systematically identify publications relevant to the use of MBSE in ship design, utilizing three databases (i.e. Dimensions.ai, Scopus, WoS), which resulted in 79 publications mentioning MBSE and ship design in the abstract or title. Following this, a methodology was introduced to narrow down the set only to publications pertinent to the SoA of the

field. This yielded 25 publications that were examined and grouped into categories selected to answer the literature review questions set in Section 2.1.1., allowing for the analysis of the SoA.

This methodology allowed for the systematic and objective examination of the publications. This methodology, in the context of MBSE in ship design at the time of writing, captured aspects of ship design, like the low maturity of new methods and the focus on the physical layer, also captured by other discussion or literature review papers in the field of ship design [20, 25, 85, 86]. Likewise, the research gaps identified in Section 2.4. are in line with the conclusion drawn in [13] that MBSE methods lack an underpinning mathematical backbone. Given this alignment of the results of this study with those of other peer-reviewed literature review publications, it is concluded that the methodology used is valid and the conclusions reached should not change significantly under small changes in either the keywords used or the initial set of publications. To validate this claim, the search was executed again, with a change in keywords and by adding publications to the final set from the field of ship design using methods similar to MBSE. Subsequently, the resulting publications were examined against the research gaps identified in Section 2.4.. In both cases, the conclusions remained relevant.

Reflecting further on the systematic literature review, it becomes clear that addressing the identified gaps necessitates the introduction of an MBSE method that accounts for them. Specifically, the review highlighted the requirement for a method capable of quantifying interactions among the systems architecture layers, systematically propagating uncertainties, and enabling comprehensive yet computationally efficient design space exploration. The SEA methodology, introduced in [10], aimed to address the first gap partly, and although, in its current form, it demonstrates potential in fulfilling these requirements, practical application to large-scale, realistic scenarios common in early-stage ship design suggests that further refinement is essential. Consequently, the need emerges for a targeted refinement of the SEA methodology, aimed at enabling the identification of architectural interdependencies, without compromising its core strength in quantitatively exploring them.

3. Introducing the Systems Element Analysis (SEA) Methodology

SEA extends traditional MBSE by invoking an analogy to FEM to capture and quantify the interactions among the Operational (O), Functional (F), Logical (L), and Physical (P) layers. In SEA, each OFLP element is represented as a node within a virtual truss network, and the directed connections between nodes behave like spring elements whose stiffness is defined by production tensors. These tensors encapsulate the input–output relationships of individual components. They are assembled into a global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} , which governs how changes propagate through the entire system architecture. The different inputs-outputs and parameters of the nodes are considered analogous to the degrees of freedom (DoFs) in FEM.

Existing tools—either numerical simulations, such as the dynamic FEA solver for the shafting system used in [10], or analytical equations, like Holtrop and Mennens—are integrated into SEA by embedding their input–output mappings within the production tensors. When a DoF changes, its influence cascades through \mathbf{K} , enabling the execution of a sensitivity analysis and systematic propagation of the change’s impact across all OFLP layers. By exploring this coupled stiffness matrix under prescribed boundary conditions, SEA facilitates a quantitative exploration of the interactions between the OFLP elements, revealing trade-offs and identifying critical interdependencies early in the ship design process.

3.1. SEA as a Potential Solution to the Literature Gaps

Currently, the SEA methodology addresses the first identified literature gap by establishing a structured quantitative methodology for modeling and understanding the complex interactions within the SA. Unlike current MBSE approaches, which primarily rely on qualitative or binary relationships, SEA quantifies these interactions explicitly, following the FEM train of thought. The interactions between the elements of the SA are described using the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} . This stiffness matrix captures the interdependencies of the elements of the OFPL Layers, providing designers with actionable insights into how variations in one aspect of the architecture propagate to others. Consequently, SEA resolves the gap associated with the lack of quantitative methods for describing OFLP interdependencies.

SEA is based on the assumption that the models, empirical equations or simulations to extract the necessary trends and trade-offs exist under the knowledge of an expert, who is responsible to ensuring that each simulation’s inputs, outputs and inner workings are documented and encoded. These inputs and outputs of all the available tools and models are considered the Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) of the SA.

Previously, in [10], the DoFs were used to manually create a knowledge graph consisting of the SA’s components as nodes. This knowledge graph in SEA acts as an n -dimensional (where n is the number of the SA’s DoFs) truss network. The utility of the virtual truss network is the analogy of exerting a displacement, or change, in one DoF and observing the displacement in all other DoFs. This analogy is translated in the “spring constants” between the DoFs at each design point, and is used for the construction of the \mathbf{K} . The spring constants are a function of the design point. The mapping of the design space is created similar to FEM, by the use of “hat” or basis functions between the design points. This process is presented in Figure 7.. Furthermore, SEA’s mathematical backbone allows for the use of the same mathematical toolset as FEM.

Figure 7.: SEA Methodology schematically

This opens the doors for the use of uncertainty quantification tools, like Bayesian sampling, statistical or fuzzy FEM. The mathematical formulation with quadratures also permits the integration of methods like chaos polynomial expansion and compositional kernels.

Finally, the OFLP elements’ node formulation facilitates the separate modeling of each node by its respective owners or designers. This compartmentalization between the OFLP elements ensures the privacy of sensitive data within the nodes, with the exposed parts being the input and output DoFs. While in its current form, SEA requires the creation of the connections manually, to properly explore the interdependencies and the possible combination of components of the SA, an automated approach for creating the truss-directed network is required.

3.2. Proposed Modification of the SEA Methodology

The modification proposed in this paper for the SEA method revolves around the identification of the possible interdependencies between the elements of the SA, as discussed in Section 3.1.. To achieve this, a brute-force approach was adopted, described in Algorithm 1. This approach iterates through all the combinations of nodes. It creates a truss element, or edge, as defined in network theory, if there is a producer-consumer relationship of the nodes’ DoFs. Then, the algorithm iterates again over all the combinations of nodes and checks the output DoFs produced in the path between them against the required output DoFs, introduced as inputs to the algorithm. This procedure is defined in line 3. Finally, after all possible paths fulfilling the requirement for the output DoFs have been identified, Dijkstra’s algorithm is used to pinpoint the shortest path. The rest of the SEA Methodology, as presented in [10], remains unchanged.

Algorithm 1 SEA Algorithm[10], Modified

Input: OFLP Components, required Output DoFs

Output: DoF interactions, Possible SAs, and minimum viable SA

1: Initialize the Nodes and the DoFs

- 2: Create all possible Trusses \triangleright *If two nodes are connected via a DoF with one being the producer and one the consumer, create a Truss Element*
 - 3: **procedure** PATH FINDING ALGORITHM(OFLP, required Output DoFs)
 - 4: **for** Node_{*i*} in Nodes **do** \triangleright *Iterate through all the possible node combinations*
 - 5: **for** Node_{*j*} in Nodes **do**
 - 6: **if** Path \exists from Node_{*i*} to Node_{*j*} **then**
 - 7: Gather the output DoFs from the Nodes in Path
 - 8: **if** Output DoFs \supseteq Required DoFs **then** Save Path-Network
 - 9: **end procedure**
 - 10: Find Shortest Path \triangleright *Utilizing Dijkstra's Algorithm*
 - 11: **procedure** DESIGN SPACE CREATION(OFLP, BCs, Path-Network) \triangleright *As described in [10]*
 - 12: Store Design Point
 - 13: **end procedure**
 - 14: Perform Sensitivity Study
-

To demonstrate the functionality of this modification, a proof-of-concept was developed. To simplify this process and focus on the algorithm, the nodes representing the elements of the SA were replaced with nodes representing the equations used in [87]. This reduces the problem to 4 nodes, with their production functions, the relationship between their input and output DoFs being simple polynomial equations. A sensitivity study was conducted to determine which parameters, or DoFs, were the most influential. The results of this study are presented in Figure 8.. In the sensitivity plots, the vertical axis represents the sensitivity, and the horizontal axis represents the position of this sensitivity in the parameter's bounds from 0 to 100, where these numbers represent the lower and upper bounds of the parameter. The sensitivity study's results were sanity-checked with the conclusions of [87]. The main takeaway from the sensitivity study was that the most influential parameter is the x_1 , for which the sensitivity plot can be observed in Figure 8.a, with x_4 in Figure 8.b being the second most influential. This is partially verified by [87], where the paths with the most success have these two independent variables as inputs close at the beginning of the design path. The next research step is creating a design space similar to this paper.

Figure 8.: Proof-of-Concept Results

3.3. The future of SEA

While SEA shows promise in addressing the gaps identified in the systematic literature review, some steps are required to address them fully. Some of these steps, mainly the mathematical in nature, have been mentioned in Section 3.1., so this subsection will focus on the conceptual and practical application to ship design sides.

Currently, SEA is quite theoretical, and while the application described in [10] is an actual ship design case study, the modification proposed in this paper can pose challenges in an actual case study. Specifically, introducing actual SA elements will require a modification of the pathfinding algorithm to accommodate the connections between the OFLP layers. In the same vein, translating the SA elements into nodes is not always straightforward, specifically when dealing with the upper layers of the OFLP, where it becomes

increasingly difficult to describe operations, functions, and requirements in mathematical terms. Attempts to address this obstacle are in progress, as demonstrated by [11]; however, translating requirements into boundary conditions remains challenging.

Moreover, as shown in [10], modeling the SA elements into nodes presents an obstacle if the production function of multiple nodes is a simulation. In this case, the computational efficiency and parallelization of the procedure become prominent. Particularly, the question that needs to be addressed is how a procedure involving several black box procedures, or production functions, for which the computational cost is not known and different from each other, can be parallelized to achieve maximum computational efficiency.

4. Conclusion

This study began by asking how far MBSE has matured in ship design and whether its current tools suffice to capture the intricate interdependencies and uncertainties inherent in early-stage concept exploration. Our systematic review revealed that, despite growing interest, MBSE applications in naval architecture remain fragmented, largely confined to isolated subsystems or used qualitative linkages, and seldom address uncertainty across OFLP layers. To close these gaps, we proposed the SEA methodology, which casts every system element as a node in a virtual truss and assembles their input–output relationships into a global stiffness matrix. By embedding existing analytical and simulation models as production tensors, SEA transforms traditionally binary or heuristic connections into fully quantitative DoF interactions, enabling rigorous sensitivity and uncertainty analyses through established finite-element techniques.

A simplified proof-of-concept confirmed that SEA correctly identifies key drivers of system behavior and reproduces known trends, demonstrating its potential to guide naval architects and systems engineers through concept exploration studies. Implementing SEA at scale will require a formal semantic framework to translate high-level requirements into boundary conditions and efficient parallelization of heterogeneous “black-box” models. Once these practical challenges are met, SEA promises to unify multidisciplinary teams under a common mathematical paradigm, systematically explore alternative architectures, and ensure that early design decisions are robust to uncertainty—thereby fulfilling the original goal of elevating MBSE from a collection of case studies to a truly predictive, uncertainty-aware foundation for next-generation ship design.

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